

POSITION PAPER

Universities, Policy Makers and Stakeholders fostering Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) nested systems for Societal Impact

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Introduction

Universities are operating in an ever-evolving complex context, at the crossroads of Science, Technology and Innovation systems in transition. This position paper should be viewed in the context of the increasing policy and societal demands to link excellent research with social impact and meet the challenges of capturing, assessing and measuring this impact. The debate on the social impact of research has gained a special relevance in recent decades with the introduction of the concept as one key evaluation criterion in national Science Technology and Innovation Systems, in research recognition mechanisms alongside scientific excellence, and in funding schemes. How can researchers work efficiently towards addressing the challenges of society today through ambitious research projects proposed by governmental institutions but constrained by limited funding? Who guarantees that the local reaches the global or vice-versa? How are we to best understand and implement societal impact? Should societal impact be limited to anything that connects with social actors? Overall, is the question of what knowledge is needed for "social impact" and how to best design, implement, monitor and measure research projects for that social impact.

As a result of a constructive collaboration and shared concerns on this topic, international experts gathered at the University of Deusto in September 2018 to consider appropriate responses to this challenge. This paper presents the main messages coming out of the workshop "*With the hands in dough*": *Paving the way to the social impact dimension of research*'.

1. Adopting a more systemic humanistic approach in a technologically driven world

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Research with social impact puts ‘society’ at the heart of science, technology and innovation systems; a ‘society’ that is not exclusively technology-driven but one that builds on the potential of technologies to make a “new human centered society”.

2. Aligning local and regional actions with global goals through multi-stakeholders partnerships

Research and innovation with social impact should align local and regional initiatives with global societal goals in a process of participatory design and co-creation through multi-stakeholders partnerships.

3. Transitioning from disciplinary to transdisciplinary inter-sectoral collaborations is not sufficient

Despite the relevance of transitioning from disciplinary to interdisciplinary and to transdisciplinary intersectoral collaborations, we feel that this is not sufficient to help us pose the right questions and find the right answers. Instead, these co-operations should help us better co-define achievable and realistic purposes and goals in order to influence behaviour which would bring-about change and impact society.

4. Designing evaluation, measurement and assessment mechanisms for social impact

Measuring, monitoring and evaluating social impact varies significantly by research discipline. At the proposal design stage, researchers should make clear what kind of societal change they want to achieve, how and with whom. Societal partners need to recognise the role of the research in achieving these changes and be able to show tangible evidence of this impact. During the evaluation process, robust evidence is needed with regards to the project goals. Impact methods, tools and assessment exercises and mechanisms serve as a means (never as an end in itself) to explain the project evaluation process in its broader context of society as a whole. **It is important to be aware that societal impact cannot be attributed solely to the action of one project and cannot be determined merely on completion of the project.**

5. Integrate social impact in the strategy of research institutions

Social impact should be an integral part of universities’ research strategies. However, the debate should not be limited solely to one single institution but to the university system as a whole, a living context constantly undergoing a process of transition and redefinition to respond to local, regional and global challenges.

6. Promoting different forms of science transfer

Research results should go beyond the academic and scientific communities and reach society from a coherent societal intervention logic perspective. The transfer of the developed knowledge and research outcomes to intermediate and final users has to be evidenced according to the pre-established quantifiable indicators for measuring the potential societal impact of the expected results. Academia should be able to “translate” and communicate its scientific knowledge into impactful non-academic contributions offering useful guidelines/tools and recommendations directly applicable to the targeted beneficiaries.

7. Conclusion: Developing STI strategies fostering nested systems for societal impact

A culture of social impact needs to be enhanced in all spheres, integrating a myriad of perspectives (such as societal needs, an integrated value chain, inter- and transdisciplinary research, institutional vision, impact monitoring and measurement) in a nested system.

Universities, Policy Makers and Stakeholders fostering Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) nested systems for Societal Impact

***'By adopting more humanistic approaches in a technologically driven world, we will be able to align local and regional actions with global goals and to develop STI strategies capable of fostering nested systems for societal impact.'*³**

Universities are operating in an evolving complex context, at the crossroads of Science, Technology and Innovation systems in transition. This position paper should be viewed in the context of increasing policy and societal demands to link excellent research with social impact and the challenges of capturing, assessing and measuring this impact.

The debate on the social impact of research has gained a special relevance in the last decades with the introduction of the concept in national Science Technology and Innovation Systems⁴; in research recognition mechanisms alongside scientific excellence and in funding schemes as one key evaluation criterion.

How can researchers achieve impact through ambitious projects proposed by governmental institutions but constrained by limited funding? Questions on how these systems are designed arise constantly. Who do they serve? Who guarantees that the local reaches the global or vice-versa? Should societal impact be limited to anything that connects solely with social actors? Overall, consideration should be given to a) what the research scope should be to achieve societal impact, b) what knowledge is needed for "social impact", c) how best to design implement, monitor and measure research projects for social impact and d) who should be involved in such research endeavours.

As a result of a constructive collaboration and shared concerns on this topic, international experts gathered at the University of Deusto in September 2018 to consider appropriate responses to this challenge. The seminar *'With the hands in the dough⁵: Paving the way to the social impact dimension of research'* approached critical elements regarding the academia's capacity to generate social impact, the role of social sciences and humanities, 'reflection in action' or 'hands-on research', among others. Within this scope, questions arose about what types and amounts of investments and partnerships are being made, and/or need to be put in place, to align four socio-

³ This was the key conclusion of the workshop *'With the hands in dough: Paving the way to the social impact dimension of research'*, held at the [University of Deusto](https://www.unideusto.org/) in September 2018. Leading international, national and regional experts gathered together to discuss with DEUSTO research community the concept of social impact, approaches, implementation mechanisms and evaluation methodologies. José María Guibert and Rosa Santibañez (Rector and Vice-Rector for Research and Knowledge Transfer of the University of Deusto), Adolfo Morais (Deputy-Minister for Universities and Research of the Basque Government) and Harald Hartung (Head of Unit at the European Commission) met for a two day debate with experts from Japan, Belgium, the Netherlands, Canada, the United Kingdom and Finland to discuss the challenges ahead for Science, Technology and Innovation Systems.

⁴ The United Kingdom Research Excellence Framework (REF): <https://www.ref.ac.uk/>. In the Netherlands, the government adopted in 2011 a "top sectors" approach: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/policies/top+sectors>. And The Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO) has also launched the NWO-WOTRO Science for Global Development Initiative: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/about-nwo/organisation/nwo-domains/wotro/Impact+toolkit>. Beyond Europe, the Impact Canada Initiative: <https://www.canada.ca/en/innovation-hub/topics/impact-canada-initiative.html>; or the Australian Government Social Impact Investing Initiative: <https://treasury.gov.au/programs-initiatives-consumers-community/social-impact-investing/>

⁵ 'With the hands in the dough' in the sense of "hands on the issue".

political interconnected spheres in the quadruple helix of academia, industry, government and society; or within more systemic approaches such as Harayama's Society 5.0 concept.

The innovative approach of this joint reflection was the concurrence of diverse stakeholders' perspectives, sometimes with confluent and complementary views, and also bringing in conflicting interests, modes of operating and timings. Consequently, this position paper adopts a systems thinking approach.

Bilbao workshop conclusions and key messages are presented in this paper as a progressive and forward-looking joint position statement.

KEY MESSAGES

1. Adopting a more systemic humanistic approach in a technologically driven world

There has been much discussion on the concept of ‘Social Impact of Research’. In our understanding the debate on Social Impact should follow a **systems thinking approach**. In the current context of increasingly interconnected, interdependent and globalised societies, systems thinking helps us adopt a holistic understanding of our societies, focusing on the way the disparate parts of systems interrelate, operate and develop overtime and, ultimately, exist within wider systems⁶. Therefore, “...getting along in this complex world of complex systems requires more than technocracy” (Meadows, 2009:167).

As Meadows⁷, Arnold and Wade⁸ state “*systems thinking consists of three kinds of things: elements (characteristics), interconnections (the way these characteristics relate to and/or feed back into each other), and a function or purpose*”. This holistic approach enables us to confront the main societal challenges we are facing today from a **more humanistic and social purpose perspective**.

The utilitarian view of research, debated since the turn of the 20th century, conceives research with societal impact as one producing useful results **and bringing benefits for society**. Nowadays, there is a growing consensus that the impact of research is multi-faceted and extends not only beyond the academic, but also beyond the merely economic impact (the European Commission included this idea in the Ricci report in 2005⁹). Despite this, the political discourse continues to be dominated by the idea of the economic benefits of research¹⁰.

In alignment with the systems thinking approach, systems behaviour (in our case, the activity emanating from the research process) results from the effects of reinforcing and balancing processes where feedback loops are an essential component. In our perspective, in order to jointly consider and capture the whole value of research, **social impact should be understood as a multifaceted ever-evolving process**.

In our view, the term ‘Social Impact’ should be used as “potential social influence” or “influence for social change and transformation”.

Whilst business may see these responses as exclusively or mainly technology-driven, we believe that the proposed solutions should emerge from a **more humanistic and social perspective**.

⁶ Teach target. *System Thinking*. Retrieved from <https://searchcio.techtargget.com/definition/systems-thinking>

⁷ Meadows, D. H. (2008) *Thinking in Systems: A Primer*. White River Junction, VT: Chelsea Green Publishing.

⁸ Arnold, R.D & Wade, J.P. (2015) *A Definition of Systems Thinking: A Systems Approach*. 2015 Conference on Systems Engineering Research. Procedia Computer Science 44 (2015) 669 – 678

⁹ European Commission: Assessing the Social and Environmental Impact of European Research. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, 2005. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/research/evaluations/pdf/archive/fp6-evidence-base/evaluation_studies_and_reports/evaluation_studies_and_reports_2005/assessing_the_social_and_environmental_impacts_of_european_research_report_2005.pdf

¹⁰ Molas-Gallart, J. (2014) *Research evaluation and the assessment of public value*, Arts and Humanities in Higher Education, 14, 111-126. Georghiou, L. (2015) *Value of research. Policy paper by the Research, Innovation, and Science Policy Experts (RISE) of the Directorate General for Research and Innovation*, European Commission. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/pdf/expert-groups/riase/georghiou-value_research.pdf

Research with social impact should be seen in a wider systemic sense of the “societal” dimension, contributing to processes of change or transformation and including the social, cultural, environmental and economic returns produced by research results (outputs) or products (outcomes). The final objective is that research results go beyond the academic and scientific communities and **reach the whole society** (policymakers, practitioners and citizens).

Likewise, we should consider the important role played by **social sciences and humanities**, as they bring the humanistic and ethical elements to the fore and help provide the answers to the growing research and innovation dilemmas such as what type of practical and ethical questioning should industries and universities be posing to improve the relevance and reach of social impact research (e.g. the changing nature of labour and the influence on society and industry).

2. Aligning local and regional actions with global goals through multi-stakeholders partnerships

Research with social impact puts ‘**society**’ at the heart of science, technology and innovation systems; a ‘society’ that is not exclusively technology-driven but one that builds on the potential of technologies to shape a “**new human centered society**”, as supported by Yuko Harayama and Mayumi Fukuyama¹¹. According to Yuko Harayama, “*we need for more humanistic values in a technologically driven world; (...) we need to move to the Society 5.0*”.

The concept of Society 5.0

This concept was proposed by the Japanese Cabinet in its fifth Science and Technology Basic Plan as a future society that Japan should aspire to.

It is understood as “*a human-centered society that balances economic advancement with the resolution of social problems by a system that highly integrates cyberspace and physical space*”¹².

In anticipation of the enormous and accelerated path of changes transforming our societies, and the innovation that is bringing them about, we need a “*new society that incorporates new technologies in all industries and social activities and achieves both economic development and solutions to social problems in parallel*”¹³.

From a social impact standpoint, there is a net benefit gained in bringing these different stakeholder groups together: from leveraging impact at scale, to ensuring buy-in for social impact, guaranteeing effective use of research in practical settings or serving as ombudsman to ensure a 360 degree feedback, safeguarding that all stakeholders are positively working for a social impact.

¹¹ *Society 5.0: Aiming for a new human-centered society: Japan's science and technology policies for addressing global social challenges* (2017) *Hitachi Review*, 66 (6) http://www.hitachi.com/rev/archive/2017/r2017_06/trends/index.html

¹² Cabinet Office. *Society 5.0*. Retrieved from http://www8.cao.go.jp/cstp/english/society5_0/index.html

¹³ *idem*.

There is a general consensus in today's political discourse that research and innovation should help provide the answers to the **United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**¹⁴ adopted in September 2015. The ongoing European Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 (2014-2020) already intends to address the major concerns shared by citizens and adopts a **societal challenge-based approach**, bringing together resources and knowledge across different fields, technologies and disciplines, including social sciences and humanities¹⁵.

While the focus of evaluation under past EU Framework Programmes for research has primarily been on participant characteristics, R&D inputs and EU-funded project outputs, the emphasis under Horizon 2020 is to assess its impact on Europe's scientific and technological performance and research capacity and, more widely, on the European economy and society. More concretely, Horizon Europe (2021-2027), the proposed successor of Horizon 2020, takes into consideration the contribution of the High Level Group on "Maximising the Impact of European Research and Innovation Programmes"¹⁶ and aims to "help tackle the major global challenges of our time and contribute to achieving the SDGs"¹⁷. The High Level group also suggests the introduction of a **novel missions-based approach** to translate global societal challenges into a small number of large-scale research and innovation 'missions': "these would define expected impacts across an entire portfolio of activities, rather than at the level of individual call topics.

The UN SDGs should serve as a global reference framework for defining Europe's R&I missions". Building on Professor Mazzucato report¹⁸, the proposal for Horizon Europe sets that **research and innovation missions should speak to the citizens and engage with them in co-creation with institutional players and stakeholders.**

We share the view that research and innovation with social impact should align local and regional initiatives with global societal goals in a process of participatory design and co-creation through multi-stakeholders partnerships.

Nonetheless, as discussed during DEUSTO's event, it is not enough to focus on meeting global goals; we should rather achieve global societal objectives our "own way" by **discussing, designing and implementing in response to local and regional needs and contexts** through **multi-stakeholders partnerships** bringing together **different disciplines and sectors.**

¹⁴ UN Official Website. *Sustainable development goals*. Retrieved from <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/development-agenda/>

¹⁵ European Commission (n.d.) Horizon 2020 Societal Challenges. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/societal-challenges>

¹⁶ European Commission (2017) *LAB-FAB-APP Investing in the European Future We Want. Report of the independent high level Group on maximising the impact of EU Research & Innovation programmes*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/conferences/sof/hlg_2017_report.pdf

¹⁷ European Commission (2018) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council: establishing Horizon Europe- the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Laying Down its Rules for Participation and Dissemination, Brussels, COM (2018), 435. Retrieved from https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:b8518ec6-6a2f-11e8-9483-01aa75ed71a1.0001.03/DOC_1&format=PDF

¹⁸ European Commission (2018) *Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union - A problem-solving approach to fuel innovation-led growth*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/bold-science-meet-big-challenges-independent-report-calls-mission-oriented-eu-research-and-innovation-2018-feb-22_en

Another key reflection raised during the debate was the need for analysing the added value (benefits and costs) of following this approach. There was a general agreement that benefits would most likely outweigh disadvantages, as these sorts of partnerships facilitate the creation of “institutional buy-in”, which might consequently ease institutional commitment and adoption of research results and outputs. An illustration of local government buy-in was presented during the event by the Deputy-Minister for Universities and Research of the Basque Government. The Basque Government Science, Technology and Innovation Plan¹⁹ is aligned with EU Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3)²⁰, based on the collaboration of all relevant social agents, including but not limited to the University community.

Besides we need to discuss the costs/implications of this approach, which can be slow and burdensome. However, the benefits outweigh the cons, as partnerships at this level ensure commonalities of approach and reduce friction in communication, which facilitate greater social impact. We saw related examples of local government buy-in in the INSPIRA STEAM research presented during the conference by Eguiluz from Deusto.

3. Transitioning from disciplinary to transdisciplinary inter-sectoral collaborations

Despite the **relevance of transitioning from disciplinary to interdisciplinary, and to transdisciplinary intersectoral collaborations**, we feel that this is not sufficient to help us pose the right questions and find the right answers. Instead, these co-operations should **help us better co-define achievable and realistic purposes and goals**, in order to influence behaviour which would bring-about change and impact society.

In our view, a participatory model of co-creation should include the following elements:

a) **co-identification of** societal needs and challenges: active cooperation among different stakeholders since the design phase is a must for the definition of achievable and realistic results. Academia should provide the scientific knowledge for the design of informed public policies which should at the same time be integrated along with societal feedback. We saw interesting examples in this sense with the *UK Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology (POST)*²¹ and the *Spanish Ciencia en el Parlamento*²² initiatives providing advice on research evidence relating to public policy issues. The societal impact of a research project should be jointly delineated since its inception, maximising thus the potential for change. Likewise, meaningful and adequate measurement indicators should be defined at the project design phase for monitoring and evaluation purposes. The development of pertinent, consistent and robust measurement methods currently remain one of the main challenges for the international scientific community.

¹⁹ PCTI EUSKADI 2020. A Smart Specialisation Strategy Research & Innovation Smart Specialisation Strategy - RIS3. Retrieved from https://www.irekia.euskadi.eus/uploads/attachments/6312/PCTI_Euskadi_2020_en.pdf?1429183477

²⁰ European Commission (n.d.) *Smart Specialisation*. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/smart-specialisation>

²¹ UK Parliament (2018) *POST About*. Retrieved from <https://www.parliament.uk/mps-lords-and-offices/offices/bicameral/post/about-post>

²² Cienciaenelparlamento.org (2018) *¿Qué es #CienciaenelParlamento? | Ciencia en el parlamento*. Retrieved from <https://cienciaenelparlamento.org/que-es-cienciaenelparlamento/>

b) **co-definition of research questions**: a foresight approach should be embraced by a multi-stakeholders partnership during this process to jointly anticipate and explore future trends and drivers for strategic impact planning. Clear and accurate research questions should help the identification and definition of potential societal challenges, to adapt existing frameworks and guide coordinated actions involving academic and non-academic actors. It is noteworthy to mention that research questions are not always framed from the social impact lens. When framed through a social perspective problem, it can help a "what can I do" and co-creation approach.

In alignment with the Society 5.0 concept, we believe that private and public entities should invest and enter into a partnership together with the scientific community in a process of collaboration, co-creation and transfer of knowledge to **give responses to the most relevant challenges of our societies**.

c) **proposing transformations** according to the scope, aims and purpose of the research endeavours. Excellent researchers should be able to propose substantial steps going forward in the field of knowledge with the potential for generating societal changes and transformations through global, national, regional/local collaborative initiatives. In order to do this, it is crucial to provide value across the nexus among initiatives. With the involvement of a myriad of partners, each one needs to reckon that there is added value in their inclusion in social impact, generating win-win approaches. For business partners, for example, this can be reputational improvement; for academia - publications; for local authorities - response to a social problem.

d) **striving for the well-being and inclusive development of entities, communities and sectors**. Research with social impact promotes processes of change towards fairer, more diverse societies, where priority should be given to inclusive social welfare and development. Excellent social impactful scientific, technical and creative research contributes to the development of innovative knowledge, improves the quality-of-life of citizens, and enhances businesses competitiveness. Research and innovation should improve life conditions and growth through a multi-disciplinary approach for a fairer and more inclusive development. Research should aim at understanding and acting upon the structural causes and consequences of inequality and exclusion delving into social systems (e.g. economic, political and cultural), public policies, programmes and sectoral strategies pursuing social justice, inclusion and cohesion, with a human rights-based approach.

To boost these collaborative dynamics, nowadays there are growing incentives for collaboration and co-creation among stakeholders, both in governmental institutions and in academic organisations.

However, the question is how do we know whether these incentives are having a quantifiable impact or are just being practically applied. There is some literature on the evaluation of partnerships and tools²³; nevertheless key characteristics should have clear lines of communications, memorandums of understanding and effective conflict resolution structures.

²³ See the Partnership Dimension World Bank Series on Evaluation and Development at <https://www.crcpress.com/Evaluation-and-Development-The-Partnership-Dimension-World-Bank-Series/Feinstein/p/book/9780765809742>

Similarly, by putting social impact and partnerships first, this (partly) removes some of the attribution jostling arising when multiple organisations work together on a project.

4. Designing evaluation, measurement and assessment mechanisms for social impact

There are inevitable difficulties in measuring, monitoring, and evaluating societal impacts. These can vary significantly depending on the research discipline or field, be it life science, medicine, technology, engineering, mathematics, social sciences, humanities or ethics, to name a few. At the same time, when funding resources for research are limited, there is an increasing political and public demand for proof that funded research has scientific and societal impact.

That research may have important societal impacts constitutes a fantastic opportunity for researchers of social sciences and humanities to be recognised for much of the work they are doing, some of which does not always rapidly lead to a publication in a highly rated journal. Bouchard (2018) states the **statutory requirements** for even thinking about societal impact. At first, having the *adequate tools* in order to expose them. For example, the proposal format used by research granting agencies should include indicators of relevant societal impacts; make clear how societal impacts are likely to occur, for instance, via a theory of change or similar tools; and ask researchers for examples of how they achieved previous societal impacts within their research. Only through this mechanism (and partnerships as above expressed) can incentives change from the research design phase.

So, Step One in the evaluation of societal impact: researchers make clear in their proposal what kind of societal change they want to achieve, how and with whom. They can use a theory of change perspective to do that.

Secondly, in order to be able to demonstrate societal impacts, societal partners (practitioners, government, companies, etc.) need to be willing to recognize the role of the researcher in achieving them, and be able to show the tangible traces of this impact. These indicators of societal impact may vary considerably, and it is up to societal partners (including commissioners of research) to recognise the feasible lengths a researcher can reach to ensure societal impact is being achieved. Indicators that are too costly to collect are not explicitly relevant for the research, can stretch tight resources and, in fact, undermine social-impact efforts. Co-design reduces this risk and facilitates a mutual understanding of achievable indicators of social impact (and their relevant timelines).

Step Two in the evaluation process: to find robust evidence regarding the goals of the research project. This evidence can be quantitative or qualitative, for example through case studies.

Best practices on how to measure and evaluate both positive and negative societal impacts are required. Ensuring all stakeholders, whose well-being may be affected through an intervention, are explicitly brought into the impact measurement system is a net positive. There is a range of measurement tools and catalogues of societal impact metrics available in the marketplace²⁴. **Impact measurement will always remain a proxy** in some description (and not the “intrinsic” societal impact”). Therefore, impact methods, tools and assessment exercises and mechanisms

²⁴ See O’Flynn and Barnett (2016) for a discussion of social impact measurement methodologies and for social impact metrics; please refer to resources such as IRIS Indicators, UNPRI, SOPACT etc.

serve as a means (never as an end in itself) to explain this process in its broader context of society as a whole.

Research with societal impact will have different stakeholders from researcher, commissioner, local municipalities and beyond, also different causal logics, different expectations for impact and different timelines for social impacts to occur, as well as different scale effects. Researchers do not know how their products may create a downstream effect influencing others behaviour, leading to innovations that could be very large. There is a need for societal impact measurement in this regard to be pragmatic, **focus on a direct causal chain** of likely societal impact and within a sphere that can be measurable. Expectations need to be managed with regards to the level of feasible change from one research project or intervention to the other, in order not to set commissioners expectations too high.

As a result, researchers and their co-design counterparts, need to think about evaluation design as well as **research question design** (as outlined under point 3). As not all researchers can be evaluation specialists, more needs to be done to create useful tools for researchers to be aware of what societal impact measurement/evaluation design is most useful for them²⁵. This would allow for a more nuanced discussion at an earlier stage in research design, and facilitate adequate and meaningful criteria and indicators to assess social impact. It would also highlight the **scope (and limitations) of the evaluation design** and how much can be feasibly said at an early stage on societal impact and therefore limit expectations from stakeholder partners.

Furthermore, when engaging with evaluation, societal impact measurement and research design, a fundamental component is that the process should be bonded to a **code of ethics to ensure societal impact** is retained, and that rights are not violated. Different evaluation designs have different ethical implications; similarly different projects have different requirements for consent, access and improving livelihoods. This means that indicators should be reflective of those that lose out because of a research project or intervention.

Step Three in the evaluation process: peer review needs to be broadened.

Peer evaluation needs to be adapted so as to not only rely upon the impact factor of scientific publications but also on the societal relevance of research. Peer reviews should be extended to expert review and allow for **non-academic experts to participate in the review process**. Not wanting to underestimate the performativity of assessment tools, we need to be vigilant that the effects of valorising societal impacts may not be cancelled out by the unwillingness of the academic world to accept valorising them.

In summary, the following **recommendations** can be made: introducing *theories of change* as criteria for investment selection, which is grounded in realistic benchmarks. Similarly, *incorporating project design and evaluation design for societal impact from the outset of projects* is an essential requirement, as is ensuring co-design of relevant indicators and benchmarks, and projects through structured dialogue. Finally, consideration should be given for *complexity throughout evaluation design* (particularly across varied disciplines).

²⁵ A good example of this is Befani (2016) .See <https://www.bond.org.uk/resources/evaluation-methods-tool>

Taking advantage of best practice on the evaluation marketplace and putting ethical considerations for societal impact first will ensure that the assessment of societal impact is better placed to reflect the realities of that impact.

5. Integrate social impact in the strategy of the research institutions

Academic institutions are expected to carry out high quality and excellence driven research from the idea shaping phase to the implementation and measurement of the created impact. Researchers are evaluated using still blurred indicators - *traditional evaluation methodologies and standards*, anchored in classical ways of understanding research and innovation and mainly focused on scientific excellence and metrics.

Could it be that by measuring the impact through rankings and citations we are only measuring one aspect of knowledge? Could it be that such measurements are not paying attention to the impact on society?

Social impact can, and should, play an important role in the research strategy of universities. This is an open debate not solely limited to one university or institution but to the university system as a living context, which is constantly undergoing a process of transition and redefinition. We need to intersect this transition by working with political, academic, university, research bodies and businesses/companies.

According to Phipps, by linking these together there is collaboration between those responsible for public policies and funding research, those in charge of developing institutional policies / plans and student funding, and those in direct contact with end users - partners, practitioners, students, and stakeholders (David Phipps, 2018).

Universities increasingly face growing demands from different stakeholders to generate trans-disciplinary and intersectoral collaborative and impactful research. Policy makers, research funding agencies, professionals, end-users and society in general require academia to feed into policy decision making when developing ground-breaking solutions and alternative models, to take into account public expenditure and the usefulness of the funded research. In other words, to reach society, as well as scientists, investment in research should have an economic and social return.

As a *regional example*, the new Basque University Plan includes indicators to measure the impact of research using *RIS Smart Specialisation Strategy*. This is a way of bringing the world of research closer to the priorities and needs of the immediate setting. Amongst the indicators some are focused on traditional transfer indicators (patents), but also introduce *collaborative research* with other relevant stakeholders like businesses and other non-entrepreneurial entities, the considered return on investment, costs incurred on research using private finance, and also research in association with stakeholders in Basque Science, Technology and Innovation Network. In its call for financing Research Groups, the Basque Government recognises the importance of social impact stating that basic funding should “facilitate and promote research activity, as well as improve the quality of knowledge, the social impact and the international visibility of the research undertaken by the groups within university departments in the Autonomous Community of the Basque Country.” *Assessment criteria include “the relevance and the social, economic, and technological impact of the results groups aim to achieve; the possibility of transferring the results in the short and medium term, their impact on learning and innovation*

capacity, their importance for growth, social well-being, and the environment” as well as “appropriateness to the lines of research developed by the group in response to the Basque Country Smart Specialization (RIS3) priorities”.

At the *institutional level*, the multiple implications of promoting collaboration and co-design demand the requirements of facilitation and a structured process of the core elements to cover in creation, to strengthen partnerships and networking and to play a role in the STI ecosystem.

There are **three interrelated levels** which should be impulsed simultaneously at Higher Education (HE) institutions:

The first one is the *dialogue with officials in charge of STI policies at regional, national and European levels* to understand the dynamics of change as universities are navigating in STI systems in transition. HE institutions need to adapt their internal research recognition systems to introduce the correcting measures helping them to prepare for the changes to come. We are suffering the *tensions between traditional accreditation and recognition systems*, mainly based on scientific impact, and the *growing demand for social impact recognition*.

The second one is the adaptation and *modernisation of internal research management structures and mechanisms* conceiving a performance approach embedded in the everyday ‘usual business’ of university life. This would entail integrating processes and results into performance indicators by flexibly combining novel elements (i.e., the 6i research model introduced by Antonia Caro during the workshop in Bilbao). This will be possible by a) adopting a dynamic combination of competition and collaboration; b) win-win approaches; and c) channeling the expected academic results towards energy-efficient processes that enable the valuation and assessment of both scientific and social impact alongside each other. This way HE institutions will be better equipped to foster engagement, respond to societal challenges and achieve a greater impact.

The third one is addressing researchers’ agency to *boost excellence and promote real and solid inter and transdisciplinary, intersectoral and international collaborations*. This should be done recalibrating the burdensome of heavy requirements added to the researcher’s workload.

6. Promoting different forms of science transfer

Research results should go beyond the academic and scientific communities and reach society (policymakers, practitioners and citizens) from a coherent societal intervention logic perspective. Partnerships enable the four socio-political spheres to work closer together in order to achieve meaningful and possible social impact with research e.g., scientific advances in industry; policy reshaping in government; knowledge sharing in academia; strategic reframing and reflection-in-action in companies; and mechanisms of social development and co-creation with society.

The transfer of the developed knowledge and research outcomes to intermediate and final users has to be evidenced according to the pre-established quantifiable indicators for measuring the potential societal impact of the expected results. Academia should be able to “**translate**” (and communicate) **its scientific knowledge into impactful non-academic contributions** offering useful guidelines/tools and recommendations directly applicable by the targeted beneficiaries. However, not all scientific knowledge will have non-academic contributions in a short enough time

period. Furthermore, we need to differentiate social impact-driven research from fundamental research as it is crucial *to avoid the instrumentalisation of all scientific activities*.

As well as this, *how the researcher can avoid appearing biased* when seeking to publish or disseminate his work, for example, in relation to industrial PhDs, or projects co-financed by companies. A key reputational component here is the integrity of the researcher and the company, which is the subject of the research and requires anonymity. This would need to be clarified by the researcher from the outset of the project. If a researcher cannot rely on the project being substantially unbiased, then from the academic point of view the researcher may have difficulty in getting her/his work published, and from the social impact point of view, the reliability of the results of the research are called into question.

Aside from the communicational aspect, misunderstandings could also derive from cultural barriers within the organisations. As outlined during the seminar, there is a *pressing need for institutionalising a culture of partnerships in research*, which according to Sweeny needs to be more than a trend. Partnerships enable the four socio-political spheres to work closer together in order to achieve meaningful and possible social impact with research e.g. scientific advances in industry; policy reshaping in government; knowledge sharing in academia; strategic reframing and reflection-in-action in companies; and mechanisms of social development and co-creation with society.

This partnership aspect is a growing presence in universities and public entities, such as the collaborations proposed in the Basque Country. As Adolfo Morais pointed out, the Basque Government recognises the need for increasing its financial support to research and innovation. However, the Basque industry is not following this growing investment trend for collaboration and co-creation and this could be a factor stalling the progress of the local scientific community.

Conclusion: Developing STI strategies fostering nested systems for societal impact

A culture of social impact needs to be enhanced in all spheres, from researchers to social partners, including institutions adjudicating funds and evaluating the performance and impacts of research. Building such a culture involves translation and arbitration of tensions between some of the logics of the academia and of social impacts: e.g. *social influence vs. autonomy of researcher; collective processes vs. individual career promotion; multidisciplinary projects vs. disciplinary assessment*. Moreover, it involves addressing the methodological issues of impact assessment as such: causality; attribution; contribution; (intermediate) results; timeline; incommensurability;...

Research needs to take into account the context or any other previous or simultaneous developments, etc. And it is noteworthy that in most research endeavours, *societal impact cannot be attributed solely to the action of one project, and cannot be determined merely on completion of the project*.

To accelerate the implementation of the global goals, local and regional governments should scale up priorities and actions aligned with SDGs, develop participatory models and craft multi-

stakeholders partnerships²⁶. These approaches foster co-creating processes and building new relationships for better tackling societal challenges.

However, some *conditions can help to embrace partnership research on social innovation and the assessment of its social impacts*: building partnership settings at arms-length from private funders' influence; developing assessment tools for research processes, not only impacts; adopting robust but supple sets of indicators to match various disciplinary contexts; institutionalise a culture of reciprocal knowledge transfer between partners and researchers.

We will be better equipped to activate collaborative frameworks by **leveraging interplay and synergies** between projects and larger policy initiatives; stakeholders and disciplines; and societal needs with research endeavors and innovations. As active partner of this collaboration, academia is called to be a facilitator between government and society proposing innovative models and solutions supported by excellent research with social impact.

Collaboration and co-creation are means to progress towards the creation of nested systems aligned with the Society 5.0 concept. The elaboration of ambitious projects needs to be the result of efficiently established communication and networking; and adequate inter and transdisciplinary approaches among universities, governments and industries. In *Japan*, project proposals are closely developed among researchers and public and private entities with the *objective to obtain plausible/realistic conclusions*. Among the different entities, the achievement of a common ground is essential for successful and impactful partnerships. From the starting point of the development of a proposal, there are high expectations for the outcomes of a project from all parties, i.e., for its added knowledge and value, its influence, and for the deliverables it may provide to the funders, and, finally, for the contribution and impact it may have in society.

However, reality is challenging and may go on different paths to reach the final results. Hence, close collaboration would help to better visualize the complexity that research entails and the needed support to achieve plausible outcomes.

Like in a nest, '**nested systems**' are contextual and focus on protecting the most vulnerable ones, those that cannot survive for themselves without the help and assistance of the community. They are *ecosystems fostering 'win-win' balanced interconnections, and a mix of cooperation and competitiveness* needed to achieve wellbeing, development, sustainability and inclusion. Nested systems will integrate a myriad of perspectives:

- **Societal needs perspective**: Scientific research should be more explicit on resolving societal needs of citizens and understand better the theory of change needed to bring these innovations in society;
- **Integrated value chain perspective**: Scientific research is an important leverage to identify, validate and optimise new solutions to solve societal challenges and fulfill unserved societal needs. Although scientific research is often a key part of societal innovation and renewal, it depends always on other partners in the value chain to absorb the knowledge and to bring it to the society. As a result, incorporating a societal impact focus in research and academic centres

²⁶ United Cities and Local Governments (2018) *Towards the localization of the SDGs - 2nd report*. Retrieved from [https://www.gold.uclg.org/sites/default/files/Towards the Localization of the SDGs.pdf](https://www.gold.uclg.org/sites/default/files/Towards%20the%20Localization%20of%20the%20SDGs.pdf)

demands a more integrated value chain approach to develop a coherent societal intervention logic;

- **Inter- and transdisciplinary research perspective:** Research is often very specific and focus only on a subpart of the solution set needed to generate impact. Therefore research institutions will have to embrace collective impact approaches where inter and transdisciplinary research is essential towards a system approach to overcome isolated impact;

- **Institutional perspective:** Research institutions will need to develop a strategic framework of smart specialisation of impact areas to reach excellence. This needs to be established on institutional strategy of the university (new policies on HR, governance,..) to embed and focus on impact area

- **Impact measurement and monitoring perspective:** Research institutions should monitor their societal impact and its progress. Just as they do their scientific production and impact. "Impact" has become one of the three award criteria experts need to take into consideration in the evaluation process. Horizon 2020 Key Performance Indicators are focused on assessing the impact at both project and programme level. European Commission proposal for the future programme Horizon Europe is designed to further maximise this impact and proposes three categories of "key impact pathway indicators": scientific, societal and economic/innovation impact indicators.

- **TTO perspective:** Research institutions will need to develop new instruments of technology transfer for societal impact.

We need to find a common language to define first and to measure, afterwards, social impact **looking for a more inclusive and broader concept of impact in dialogue with scientific impact.**

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Learn more at: [Workshop 'With the hands in the dough: Paving the way to the social impact dimension of research'](#)